

SOSIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS IN MALUKU FROM 2014-2020

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Abstract

This research aims to determine social and economical characteristic in Maluku Province. This research is a descriptive quantitative. The data sources issecondary data from 2014 to 2020 in Maluku Province. The parameters are independent variables (economy, regional expenditure, and poverty) and dependent variable (human development index). The regression analysis is statistical analysis.The research results show that economic, regional expenditure haa a positive HDI, while poverty had a negative HDI.Poverty has a negative impact at the level of 0.05% on the HDI in Maluku Province, which means that when poverty decreases, the Human Development Index increases. Southeast, Ambon and Seram regions suggested a job opportunities

Keywords: HDI, Economic Growth, Regional Expenditure, Poverty.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesiahas Maluku Province with the natural and economicresources. Human development in Maluku continues to progress during the period of 2014 until 2020. In 2020, the HDI in Maluku has been reaching 69.49 or growing by 0.06 % and increasing 0.04 points compared to the previous year. Efforts to increase Indonesia's HDI certainly cannot be separated from the simultaneous efforts to increase the regencies/cities HDI in Indonesia, in which one of them is Maluku Province. During 2014 to 2020, Maluku's HDI shows a great progress, the status of Maluku's human development is still stagnant. As Maluku's HDI is ranked 26 out of 34 provinces in Indonesia(BPS, 2021).

Socio-economic characteristics are a description of the development of human development based on several basic components of quality of life and a decent standard of living.In development planning, HDI can also function to provide guidance to determine priorities in policies and establishing programs (Ferrannini et al., 2021).HDI also includes a physical and non-physical qualities of the people/community. Those 3 indicators are: health indicators(Hassanipour-Azgomi et al., 2016), education level(Willems, 2015), and economic indicators(Grubaugh, 2015). Physical quality is assessed from life expectancy, while non-physical quality is assessed from the average population and expected length of schooling, as well as indicators of economic ability, such as real expense per capita. The success of a development, especially in human development, can be assessed thoroughly by looking at how much the most basic problems within the society can be overcome(Parthasarathy et al., 2021).

Economic Growth in each Regency/City from 2014-2020 has increased and decreased differently every year. East Seram Regency/City experiences a decline in Economic Growth every year, while in 2020, high economic growth is still occupied by Ambon City. To increase economic growth, operational costs are needed which is commonly referred as regional budgets and expenditures (APBD). Regional financial management cannot be separated from the management of regional income and expenditure budgets, or the regional revenue and expenditure budgets (APBD) which becomes relevant and important for regional governments. The APBD must be managed properly, and the available funds must be used properly to improve public services and welfare. With the achievement of the regional goals that have been set, the performance of the regional government can be observed. The most basic problems are illiteracy, poverty (Ladi et al., 2021), unemployment (Soler et al., 2018), and food security (Nunes et al., 2020). However, the point is, the achievements of human development altogether are very diverse such as successful development and failure development. In this case, the government pays great attention to human development. In general, human development refers to the quality standards set (UNDP, 2020). This research aimed to determine social and economical characteristic in Maluku Province in Maluku Province.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

In this research, the locations studied included all regencies/cities in Maluku Province within a period of 7 years, from 2014-2020. The source of data were secondary data namely data collection agencies and published to the public using data. In this research, the data used are secondary data published by the Central Bureau of statistics (BPS), agencies, and other institutions that are still relevant to the variables studied. The data collected are as follow HDI Development Data for Regencies in Maluku Economic Growth Data for 11 Regencies/Cities in Maluku Province, Regional Expenditure Data for 11 Regencies/Cities in Maluku Province, Percentage of Poverty Data for Regencies in Maluku.

Research Variable

The research variable have two variables (independent variable and dependent variable). The independent variables are: Economic Growth (X1), Regional Expenditure (X2), and Poverty (X3). Dependent Variable. The dependent variable is a variable in which the value depends on another variable. The dependent variable is often called the response variable which is symbolized by Y. Human Development Index is a dependent variable

The variables and their operations are explained as follows: **Human Development Index (Y)** According to the Central Bureau of Statistics such as health, education, and economic aspects. In this research, the data used is from all regencies in Maluku from 2014-2020 which is taken from the Central Bureau of Statistics and presented in percent units.

Economic Growth (X1) Economic growth of a region is obtained from the increase in GRDP at constant prices which reflects the increase in the production of goods and services from year to year. Economic growth as the independent variable in this research is the changes in Gross

Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) based on 2010 constant prices from 2014-2020 in Maluku Province. **Regional Expenditure (X2)** Regional Expenditure is all regional obligations recognized as deductions from the value of net assets in the period of the relevant fiscal year, expressed in Rupiah (Law number 32 of 2004 article 1 paragraph 16). **Poverty (X3)** Poverty is a condition in which a person cannot fulfil his/her basic right to maintain and develop a dignified life. In this research, the data on the percentage of poor people in percent who are below the poverty line in 11 regencies/cities of Maluku Province for the period of 2014-2020 are used.

Data Analysis Method

Estimation of Panel Data Regression

The data analysis used is panel data regression analysis which is used to estimate economic growth, regional expenditure, and poverty on the human development index.

The Panel Regression Model from this research is formulated as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + e$$

Note : Y : HDI, α : Constant, X1 : Economic Growth, X2 : Regional Expenditure, X3 : Poverty, β (1, 2, 3): Independent variable coefficient, t : Time, i : Maluku Province, e : error term

Model Selection

There are three tests to choose panel data estimation techniques, that are **Chow Test, Hausman Test**

Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2)

The coefficient of determination (R^2) is used to measure how far the model's ability to explain the variation of the independent variables. Partial Significance Test (T Test).

T test statistic is used to test the effect of each independent variable which is used partially. Simultaneous Testing (F Test).

This test is carried out to find out simultaneously whether the independent variables have a significant effect or not on the dependent variable. This test is carried out using a two-way test with the following hypothesis: $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$, $H_0: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq \beta_5 \neq 0$

Determine the level of significance of 0, 05 ($\alpha = 5\%$)

Determination of the value of Fcount can be calculated by the following formula:

$$F_{\text{count}} = \frac{R^2 / (k - 1)}{(1 - R^2) (n - k)}$$

Information: R^2 : Determinant coefficient, Number of observations, k: Number of Variables

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Condition of Economy in Maluku Province

Figure 1 explains that Economic Growth in each Regency/City from 2014-2020 has increased and decreased differently every year. East Seram Regency/City experiences a decline in Economic Growth every year, while in 2020, high economic growth is still occupied by Ambon City. To increase economic growth, operational costs are needed which is commonly referred as regional budgets and expenditures (APBD). Regional financial management cannot be separated from the management of regional income and expenditure budgets, or the regional revenue and expenditure budgets (APBD) which becomes relevant and important for regional governments. The APBD must be managed properly, and the available funds must be used properly to improve public services and welfare. With the achievement of the regional goals that have been set, the performance of the regional government can be observed.

Figure 1: Regencies/Cities Economic Growth Rate in Maluku Province For the Period of 2014-2020

Brida et al., (2020) shows that in developed countries there are economic growth policies. The independent variables found to be significantly related to HDI growth are population size, population growth, and initial level of GDP. The difference between the two models cannot be explained simply because the HDI measures the same effect as GDP. Limiting the sample to developing countries only and estimating the model using the ranking order of the country's HDI did not change the results (Grubaugh, 2015).

3.2 Regional Expenditure in Maluku

Figure 2 explains that the fluctuations of the expenditure movement in Maluku Province for the 2014-2020 budgeting from the aspect of Regional Expenditure shows an increase and decrease

in expense for the period of 2014-2020. In 2020, the regency/city of Buru experiences a decrease in expense by 335.06 billion (IDR). The increase of Regional Expenditure in 2020 is occupied by Central Maluku regency/city.

Figure 2: Regional Expenditure by Regencies/Cities in Maluku Province For the Period of 2014-2020

Poverty had an effect expenditure. The differences of study revealed that the government has challenges regarding poverty, namely employment and gross regional domestic product (GRDP) (Elia et al., 2020).

3.3. Percentage of the Poor Regency/City in Maluku Province

Figure 3, it is noticed that regencies/cities in Maluku Province during 2014 to 2020 experience a decline and increase differently every year. In 2020, the Southwest Maluku City Regency experiences a high poverty rate of 29.19 percent compared to other Regencies/Cities. And the position of the low or reduced poverty rate is occupied by Ambon City, roughly by 4.51 %. Thus, Maluku province is still classified as the fourth poorest province in Indonesia.

Figure 3: Percentage of the Poor Regency/City in Maluku Province for the Period of 2014-2020

Davies & Quinlivan (2006) revealed that increased trade is positively associated with increased future social welfare. The percentage measurement of the dependent variable used the regression model. This calculation is intended to find out a good decision in the analysis indicated by the magnitude of the coefficient of R^2 determination. Table 1 above explains that the significance value of the Economic Growth variable in the Southeast, Seram, Ambon, and Maluku which are very dominant is the Ambon region with a significance of 0.0006 at a standard prob of 0.05%.

Table 1: Significance Value on HDI in Four Regions

Region	Significance value		
	Economic Growth	Regional Expenditure	Poverty
Southeast	0.0080	0.0000	0.0000
Seram	0.2738	0.0046	0.0252
Ambon	0.0006	0.2475	0.0001
Maluku	0.2824	0.0000	0.0000

Table 1 also explains the significance value of the Regional Expenditure variable in the Southeast, Seram, Ambon, and Maluku regions, which are very dominant in the Southeast and Maluku regions with a significance of 0.0000. In the Poverty variable, the very dominant significance value is the Southeast and Maluku regions with a significance of 0.0000 at a standard prob of 0.05%. Poverty has an effect on HDI in the Southeast, Seram, Ambon and Maluku Regions. Estimation of analysis and discussion can be derived regarding the effect of

independent variables (economic growth, regional expenditure, and poverty) on HDI in Maluku.

3.4. Economic Growth in Maluku Province

This study revealed that the economic growth variable had a positive elasticity of 0.063464 on the HDI in Maluku from 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.0000. This study revealed that economic growth changes by 1%, there will be a change in the human development index in Maluku Province of 0.063464. Southeast shows that the economic growth had a correlation (0.024500) on HDI during 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.0080. Seram Region also exposed the economical improvement (0.031781) on HDI during 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.2738. Ambon Region shows the positive economic growth variable (0.073458) on the HDI in the Ambon Region from 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.0006.

3.5. Regional Expenditure of HDI in Maluku Province

This study explained a regional expenditure had a positive impact (9.169596) on HDI in Maluku during 2014-2020. Southeast Region explained that the regional expenditure variable has a positive and significant effect with a positive elasticity of 31,27946 on the HDI in the Southeast Region from 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.0000. Seram Region explained that the expenditure variable had a positive impact (32.67083) on the HDI in Maluku during 2014-2020 (0.0046). Ambon Region explained that the regional expenditure variable has a good impact (7.516427) on HDI in Maluku 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.2475.

3.6. The Effect of Poverty on Human Development Index in Maluku Province

This study explained poverty variable has a negative elasticity (-0.171504) in HDI in Maluku from 2014-2020. The poverty ratio cause decrease by 1%, it would increase the HDI in Maluku Province for 7 years. Southeast Region explained that the poverty variable has a negative and significant effect with a negative elasticity of -0.415302 on the human development index in the Southeast Region from 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.000. The poverty in Seram Region revealed that a negative elasticity of -0.313864 on the human development index in the Seram Region from 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.0046. Poverty had a negative correlation (-0.680226) on the HDI in Maluku from 2014-2020 with a significance of 0.0000 in Ambon.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Economic growth has a positive on the human development index in Maluku, this strengthens the assumption that economic growth has not made a convincing contribution to the Human Development Index. Regional Expenditure has a positive on HDI in Maluku Province, which means that the higher regional expenditure costed, the higher the Human Development Index. All stakeholders must work together, so that poverty reduction is right on target.

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